

Analytical tools for the characterization of deamidation in monoclonal antibodies

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ABSTRACT

This review focuses on the deamidation of asparagine in monoclonal antibodies, one of the well-known degradation pathways. The importance of close monitoring of deamidation from early developability assessment to *in vivo* studies is discussed consequentially. The application of chromatographic and electrophoretic instruments for the separation of deamidated variants is described. Current mass spectrometric approaches for characterization of deamidated antibody variants and localization of modification sites are discussed accordingly. The review also covers the challenges in bioanalysis of deamidated forms in complex biological matrices during *in vivo* studies.

1. Deamidation

The deamidation of asparagine (Asn) and glutamine (Gln) residues is a hydrolytic reaction, which occurs spontaneously in proteins [1,2]. The deamidation rate of Asn is generally faster compared to Gln [3]. We will therefore focus on the deamidation of Asn-residues in proteins in this article. Deamidation of Asn leads to aspartic and isoaspartic acid forms, thereby introducing a negative charge at the deamidation site (Fig. 1) [4]. This change in physicochemical properties may affect biological characteristics of the peptide or protein such as a decrease in its binding affinity for a target receptor [4–7], although this is not always the case [8,9]. Deamidation is often referred to as a modification that happens at basic pH through a succinimide intermediate [10]. However, deamidation can also happen at acidic pH by direct hydrolysis of Asn to Asp [11,12]. In addition to deamidation of Asn, Asp may also isomerize to isoAsp, a process that passes most likely via a succinimide intermediate as well [13].

Asparagine deamidation is one of the main chemical modifications of interest for mAbs along with oxidation (mainly of methionine) and aspartic acid isomerization. Deamidation of asparagine (deamidated variants) contributes to the charge heterogeneity of a given antibody. Charge variant analysis is a part of the quality attributes for mAbs and therefore it is important in monitoring lot-to-lot consistency and stability of the product [14]. Since modifications, such as asparagine deamidation, are sensitive to environmental changes, such as a change in temperature or pH, the charge variant profile may also be affected by changes in the manufacturing process. Thus, charge variant profiling is

often required by regulatory authorities and as indicator of manufacturing process consistency.

Monitoring deamidation is also important during developability studies, early-stage studies where biophysical and chemical properties of candidate molecules are studied in order to develop a stable, manufacturable, safe, and efficacious drug [15]. Low heterogeneity (not limited to charge heterogeneity), the possibility of consistent manufacturing, long term stability in a liquid formulation are the main characteristics of an “ideal” protein drug candidate from a development point of view. The candidate molecule should not be prone to aggregation, fragmentation, and chemical degradation (modifications such as deamidation, oxidation, and isomerization). When an amino acid sequence of the variable domain of the candidate molecule(s) is available, CDR regions are monitored first to look for possible degradation hotspots. In the case of deamidation, stress studies in the formulation and at physiological pH are performed to localize hotspots followed by functional assays to evaluate the consequences of deamidation. The candidate with the most stable CDR domains is selected for the subsequent humanization process.

It is known that deamidations in peptides and proteins have different turnover rates and prediction of deamidation remains challenging [16]. Several studies were performed on the prediction of deamidation sites with a subsequent proposal of *in silico* tools for the estimation of deamidation rates from the three-dimensional structure known proteins [16–20]. Usually, when asparagine is followed by small amino acids such as glycine or serine, the rate of deamidation is higher [3,21,22]. However, this simple correlation does not always hold in the case of proteins, where the local three-dimensional structure and flexibility

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Fig. 1. Mechanism of asparagine deamidation through a succinimide intermediate. Theoretical monoisotopic masses of Asn, Asp, and isoAsp residues and of the succinimide intermediate are indicated. This figure is reprinted with permission from Ref [4].

of the region containing an Asn residue play major roles. For example, the monoclonal antibody (mAb) trastuzumab, used for the treatment of HER2-positive breast cancer, has two deamidation sites in the complementarity-determining regions (CDRs). Deamidation of light chain Asn30 (Lc-Asn-30), which is followed by threonine, occurs faster than deamidation of heavy chain Asn55 (Hc-Asn-55), which is followed by glycine [5,23]. Furthermore, there are two additional Asn residues followed by glycine in the heavy chain of trastuzumab, which are part of the Fc domain. Hc-Asn-387 is known to deamidate [5,23] while Hc-Asn-318 was not been reported to be prone to deamidation. Amino acid sequence, three-dimensional structure, conformational flexibility and solvent exposure of a given region are all important parameters determining the extent and rate of deamidation. Deamidation hot spots may be localized in so-called forced stability or stress studies at basic pH and elevated temperature. Subsequent fractionation of deamidated variants by ion-exchange chromatography facilitates their further characterization with different analytical approaches [5,23–25].

Recently Lu et al. reported results of a study where deamidation and isomerization liability of 131 clinical-stage antibodies were investigated [14]. Two different stress conditions were selected to localize hotspots for modifications: pH 5.5 at 40 °C for two weeks and pH 8.5 at 40 °C for one week. More frequent deamidation after high pH stress in CDRs L1 and H2 for NG, NT & NS motifs were observed with decreasing stability for NG > NS > NT. All deamidations (with one exception) which take place at pH 5.5 were also found at pH 8.5. It should be noted here that these were the motifs and CDRs for which most of the deamidations were observed. However, in some cases, deamidations were also found in other positions indicating that deamidation kinetics depend also on the local structure and conformation of a given mAb.

Deamidation in the CDRs can affect the affinity of a mAb to its target receptor. In most cases deamidation results in a decrease in affinity. For example, for trastuzumab, measurements by surface plasmon resonance (SPR) showed that deamidation of Lc-Asn-30 in one arm results in 83% of binding whereas deamidation of Lc-Asn-30 in both arms of the antibody leads to 58% of binding compared to the non-deamidated main form [5]. Since mAbs have up to 3 weeks half-life *in vivo* after administration to patients, deamidation is expected to occur in circulation. There are studies where deamidation was reported to occur *in vivo*. Huang et al. used LC-MS/MS to characterize and quantify the deamidation of an antibody in monkey serum after *in vivo* administration [6]. In this study, the amount of deamidation correlated with the circulation time in blood. Although deamidation in the heavy chain CDR2 in this study resulted in a 14-times reduction in binding to the target receptor according to SPR measurements, it is still unknown whether this impacts the antibody's therapeutic efficacy.

Despite having lower affinity, in most cases, deamidated forms can still bind to the target receptor. What remains unknown is whether there is a correlation between mAb deamidation and therapeutic efficacy? Should the treatment dose be adjusted due to the mAb's susceptibility to deamidation? These may be questions that need to be addressed in future research.

2. Liquid chromatography for the separation of deamidated variants

2.1. Ion-exchange chromatography

Ion-exchange chromatography (IEX) is a widely used approach for the separation of deamidated variants where the basis of separation is an electrostatic interaction between a charged stationary phase and ionic groups on the surface of the protein. Cation-exchange chromatography is most often used compared to anion-exchange chromatography [4,5,24,26–30]. However, the use of anion-exchange chromatography for the separation of deamidated variants has also been reported in the literature [31,32]. The majority of therapeutic mAbs have basic isoelectric points (pIs), as shown by Goyon et al., who used cation-exchange chromatography to profile charge variants of 23 FDA- and EMEA-approved mAbs in conjunction with either salt or pH gradients [33].

Being a non-denaturing technique, IEX allows the isolation of different variants for further characterization in terms of localization of modification sites. Deamidated variants usually elute earlier than the main peak on a cation-exchange column, and after the main peak on an anion-exchange column [5,23,24,31,32]. There are two ways for elution of charge variants from an ion-exchange column. Salt gradient-based elution is most widely used, where elution is performed by an increase of the salt concentration [24,34–36]. pH gradient-based elution is an alternative where charge variants are eluted by a gradual change of the pH of the mobile phase [26,27,30,34,36–38]. Linearity of the pH gradient is important in order to achieve a reproducible, high-resolution separation. The ionic strength of the buffers is also important, since a high ionic strength buffer results in earlier elution [23]. Comparison of the elution of charge variants of the monoclonal antibody trastuzumab on a cation-exchange column with salt and pH gradient elution is shown in Fig. 2. Salt and pH gradient elution systems are often compared in terms separation power [39]. While some studies did not find any significant differences in separation between the two elution modes [27], others showed that pH gradient separation outperformed the salt gradient separation [26,36,38]. Selection of the elution mode needs to be tested individually and might be dependent on the complexity of charge variants of the particular mAb.

Salt-mediated pH-gradient elution is another approach for the separation of charge variants of mAbs on IEX columns. The need for combining salt and pH gradients arises due to differences in ionic strength of most pH gradient buffers A and B. The additional salt gradient allows to control the ionic strength over the entire pH gradient [36,38], since a constant ionic strength along with a linear pH gradient is required to achieve better resolution and reproducible separations [34]. An alternative is to use pH gradient buffers that have a constant ionic strength across the entire pH range, as reported by Lingg et al. [26], and for which the pH gradient is linear.

Optimization of different elution modes (salt or pH gradient) may be helpful in adjusting the selectivity of the separation. However, selectivity may also be dependent on column chemistry. pH gradient separation of charge variants of the monoclonal antibody trastuzumab after a forced degradation study was performed on two cation exchange columns (Fig. 3). The forced degradation study was executed to induce modifications such as asparagine deamidation and aspartic acid isomerization. As shown in Fig. 3, the MabPac SCX-10 column had better selectivity compared to the ProPac Elite WCX column of the same column dimensions when the same gradient was applied (4 × 250 mm, 5 μm,

Fig. 2. Separation of charge variants of trastuzumab stressed in PBS pH 7.4 at 37 °C for one week with (A) salt and (B) pH gradient on a MabPac SCX-10 column (4 × 250 mm, 5 μm, Thermo Fisher Scientific). (A) Salt gradient elution conditions: mobile phase A: 10 mM MES buffer pH 6, mobile phase B: 10 mM MES buffer pH 6 and 300 mM NaCl. Gradient change: 5 to 35% B in 60 min at 0.5 mL/min flow rate. (B) pH gradient elution was performed as described before [23]. Mobile phase A: pH 8, mobile phase B: pH 10.5. Gradient change: 0–60% B in 63 min at 0.5 mL/min flow rate. The main variant of trastuzumab is indicated as M.

Fig. 3. Charge variant separation of trastuzumab stressed for 2 weeks at 37 °C in PBS on (A) MabPac SCX-10 and (B) ProPac Elite WCX columns with pH gradient separation as described in ref [23]. Mobile phase A: pH 8, mobile phase B: pH 10.5. Gradient change: 0–60% B in 63 min at 0.5 mL/min flow rate. The main variant of trastuzumab is indicated as M.

Thermo Fisher Scientific). Recently Murisier et al. performed a comparative study of recent stationary phases from different vendors available on the market concluding that selectivity depends on both column chemistry and elution mode [40].

The possibility of coupling IEX to mass spectrometry is gaining interest among researchers. Several studies have been published where authors used volatile salts/buffer systems to couple IEX to MS. Muneeruddin et al. coupled weak cation-exchange chromatography to mass spectrometry (MS) to separate conjugated variants of lysozyme with a gradient of increasing ammonium acetate from 100 mM (mobile phase A) to 1 M (mobile phase B) at pH 7 [41]. However, such an approach leads to ionization suppression and results in accumulation of salts in the source of the mass spectrometer, which affects robustness. Another approach to perform IEX-MS measurements is by pH gradient separation using volatile salts. However, when it comes to the use of volatile salts for pH gradient separation, the bottleneck is the buffering gap between pH 7 and 8, since ammonium acetate does not function as a buffer in this range [42]. In addition, it is difficult to achieve a linear change of pH over the gradient with available volatile salts. Despite these challenges, pH gradients for the separation of charge variants with further coupling to MS have been reported in the literature [30,43–46]. Fussl et al. reported an approach for the online analysis of charge variants of commercially available mAbs by IEX-MS [45]. Mobile phase A consisted of 25 mM ammonium bicarbonate and 30 mM acetic acid (pH 5.3) and mobile phase B consisted of 10 mM ammonium hydroxide and 2 mM acetic (pH 10.18). However, linearity of the pH gradient was poor requiring optimization of the gradient for each mAb. The non-linear pH gradient also affected the chromatographic resolution and peak shape. Despite hav-

ing a non-linear pH gradient, the authors were able to separate charge variants of several mAbs on a strong cation-exchange column. When it comes to the identification of deamidated forms by IEX-MS, there are additional challenges. First, since deamidation results in only a 1 Da mass increase, it requires (very) high-resolution MS to distinguish such a subtle increase in molecular weight at the protein level. Fussl et al. performed MS analysis at 35,000 resolution on an Orbitrap MS instrument [45]. Second, since IEX-MS is performed under ‘native’ conditions, the m/z range for mAbs is higher (between 4000 and 7000), meaning that it requires adapted quadrupole mass analyzers as well as ion optics/pressure regulators for the efficient transmission of heavy ions with only a few charges. Finally, IEX-MS analysis of deamidated variants relies on very accurate and reproducible measurements of a mass increase of 1 Da for each deamidation site (in case of deamidation in a single position). Such a mass increase often falls within the mass error of the measurement and can thus not be taken as proof of deamidation. Confirmation can only be obtained by further MS/MS fragmentation (which still has technical limitations at the protein level; see the corresponding chapter later on for details) or by an orthogonal approach, such as fraction collection followed by peptide mapping.

While salt gradient elution is a traditional approach in IEX, literature shows that it is often tedious and time-consuming to develop, as well as being a product (antibody)-specific method. The use of high salt can affect the robustness of the method and result in a long equilibration times, consequently increasing the overall analysis time. The pH of buffers used for salt gradient separation is of utmost importance, because it can affect the binding of mAbs. Therefore, the control of pH over the entire gradient is needed to achieve robust and reproducible

Fig. 4. Separation of native and deamidated peptides on three different commercial reversed-phase C18 columns using 0.1% FA (left side) and 0.05% DFA (right side) as mobile phase additives. Column 1: Luna Omega C18 Polar, 150 × 0.3 mm, 3 μm, 100 Å; Column 2: μPAC capLC; Column 3: Acclaim PepMap, 150 × 0.3 mm, 2 μm, 100 Å. NG corresponds to the native IYPTNGYTR* peptide, DG corresponds to the deamidated IYPTDGYTR* peptide and isoDG corresponds to the isoAsp-containing, deamidated IYPTisoDGYTR* peptide. Mobile phase A was 0.1% FA (or 0.05% DFA) in water, mobile phase B was 0.1% FA (or 0.05% DFA) in acetonitrile. The gradient change was 0.5% B/min at a flow rate of 5 μL/min. Column temperature was set to 40 °C. * indicates that this amino acid residue was stable isotope labelled.

separations [26,47]. Fekete et al. published a study where optimal conditions to perform salt gradient separation were investigated [35]. The authors concluded that low pH buffers result in longer retention times on the cation-exchange column, which consequently leads to better chromatographic resolution. Secondly, a salt concentration of 200 mM NaCl is sufficient to elute all charge variants, which was demonstrated on 10 commercial mAbs which had pI between 6.7 and 9.1. pH gradient separation has gained in popularity over recent years. Well-optimized pH gradient buffers can be used for charge-variant analysis of mAbs across a wide pI range without the need for changing buffers. Goyon et al. used commercial pH gradient buffers to profile the charge heterogeneity of around 20 commercial mAbs on a cation-exchange column [33]. Trappe et al. used the same commercial buffers for rapid charge variant analysis of mAbs [35]. Such a fast method is useful for screening of charge variant content during industrial development. The long-term stability of high-pH gradient buffers is considered a limitation of pH gradient-based separations but this can be overcome by regularly refreshing the buffer or by avoiding contact with ambient air.

2.2. Hydrophobic interaction chromatography

Hydrophobic interaction chromatography (HIC) is a nondenaturing approach that exploits the hydrophobicity of proteins for separation that has been successfully used for the analysis of mAbs [12,48], notably for antibody-drug conjugates [49]. There are some examples in the literature where HIC was used along with ion-exchange chromatography for the separation of deamidated variants of mAbs [49–52], since deamidation results also in a change in hydrophobicity. Cao et al. reported the use of HIC for the separation of deamidated variants of a bispecific antibody. Deamidation occurred in the light chain in one of the arms of the antibody, as confirmed by peptide mapping. In addition, separation of the succinimide intermediate from native and deamidated variants by

HIC was demonstrated [52]. Nowak et al. were able to separate deamidated variants of an unspecified mAb by HIC where the deamidation product was the isoaspartate form [53].

2.3. Reversed-phase chromatography

Reversed-phase liquid chromatography (RPLC) is often used for the localization of deamidation sites by LC-MS analysis at the peptide level after enzymatic digestion but it is not very suitable for separating charge variants of mAbs at the protein level. Separation of native (non-deamidated) and deamidated peptides by RPLC is often required prior to MS, since deamidation results in a 1 Da mass increase, which means that the m/z value of the first isotopologue of the non-deamidated peptide overlaps with the monoisotopic peak of the deamidated peptide (see next chapter for more details). Successful reversed-phase separation of native and deamidated peptides depends on parameters such as column dimension and chemistry, gradient slope, and the mobile phase modifier. Fig. 4 shows the separation of native and deamidated peptides on different reversed-phase C18 columns. The peptides are heavy labeled synthetic peptides that correspond to a tryptic peptide from the heavy chain CDR2 of trastuzumab (IYPTNGYTR) containing the deamidation site at Hc-Asn-55. When 0.1% formic acid (FA) was used, which is a commonly used mobile phase additive in LC-MS, separation was only achieved for 1 out of 3 columns. By changing the mobile phase additive to 0.05% difluoroacetic acid (DFA), selectivity changed considerably for all 3 columns with a general increase in column efficiency (narrower peak width) without an undue reduction in ionization efficiency. For example, separation of the non-deamidated and the isoAsp-containing deamidated peptides was now possible on column 2. Bults et al. were able to separate the different forms of the same peptide by using 10 mM ammonium acetate pH 5.5 as a mobile phase additive for buffer A [54]. These examples show that the mobile phase additive may be an easy way

Fig. 5. Analysis of an unspecified mAb by imaged capillary isoelectric focusing (icIEF). pI values of the corresponding charge variants are shown above the peaks. This figure is reprinted with permission from Ref [50].

of adjusting the selectivity for these challenging peptide separations in RPLC.

3. Electrophoretic methods for the separation of deamidated variants

Electrophoretic methods such as isoelectric focusing (IEF) gel electrophoresis or capillary isoelectric focusing (cIEF) have been used for the separation of charge variants of mAbs along with chromatographic approaches. IEF and cIEF are analytical techniques that separate according to differences in isoelectric point (pI or net charge), whereas ion-exchange chromatography separates based on differences in surface charge of a protein. Deamidation thus results in a shift to a more negative pI compared to the non-deamidated protein. For example, it has been shown on the IEF gel that deamidated variants of monoclonal antibody trastuzumab have a slightly more acidic pI compared to the non-deamidated main variant [24,26].

Imaged cIEF (icIEF) is an electrophoretic method to determine the pI values of charge variants of mAbs [55]. Compared to conventional cIEF, icIEF does not require an elution (mobilization step) of the protein for detection. Detection is performed by taking an image of the entire capillary while charge variants remain focused in the pH gradient inside the capillary by maintaining the electric potential. Salas-Solano et al. reported the results of an interlaboratory study, where the precision and robustness of icIEF was compared between 12 laboratories [56]. RSD values of less than 0.8% were calculated for the determination of pI values of charge variants. Results of the study concluded that icIEF is a reliable tool for charge heterogeneity assessment of therapeutic proteins and can be used as an alternative or complementary method in the biopharmaceutical industry. The drawback of icIEF is that it cannot be combined with downstream analyses such as MS or the analysis of deamidation sites by peptide mapping.

(i)cIEF is considered to outperform classical IEF in terms of separation power [57]. It has been reported that cIEF can separate subtle changes in pI down to 0.005 pH units [58]. King et al. showed the separation of acidic variants that are due to Asn deamidation in the light chain CDR of an unspecified mAb from its non-deamidated variant by icIEF (Fig. 5) [50]. The main variant had a pI of 7.8, while the variant deamidated in one light chain had a pI of 7.6. Deamidation in the light chain was confirmed after separation of charge variants by HIC and LC-MS-based characterization of fractionated forms. Here, a limitation of electrophoretic methods arises, since they cannot be used to obtain a sufficient amount of charge variants for further characterization, at least in most cases.

Generally, electrophoretic methods are suitable for the separation of deamidated variants of mAbs, however, an advantage of cIEF over gel IEF is the possibility to couple it to mass spectrometry. Dai et al. reported the analysis of charge variants by cIEF coupled to MS [59]. Deconvolution of the high-resolution spectra of acidic peaks indicated a mass increase of 1 Da for single deamidation and 2 Da for double deamidation. However, localization of the deamidation sites was not possible, since this would require further fragmentation of the intact antibody (top-down MS).

Coupling of CE to MS is challenging. The use of a sheath liquid that is added at the end of CE capillary to provide electrical contact and assist the electrospray in the MS source results in considerable dilution of analytes consequently affecting sensitivity. This challenge can be addressed using a sheathless CE-MS interface, however, the choice of sheathless CE-MS interfaces is limited. Han et al. reported coupling CE to TOF MS with a nanospray interface driven by the electroosmotic flow and an added sheath liquid for the analysis of charge variants of mAbs at the subunit level [60]. Interestingly, to achieve better separation, the system required acetic acid in the range between 5 and 30% as background electrolyte and the amount of acetic acid had to be adjusted for each mAb. To evaluate the ability of the system to separate deamidated forms, deamidation was induced and the mAb was digested with IdeS followed by disulfide bond reduction and CE-MS analysis. The succinimide form of the Fd domain was electrophoretically separated from the Fd domain, however, the authors did not report the detection of the deamidated Fd domain indicating that native and deamidated Fd forms were not separated.

Carillo et al. reported native mass spectrometric analysis of charge variants by the use of MS-compatible background electrolytes in the ZipChip® CE system [61]. The authors reported that this CE-ESI-MS platform is a fast and robust tool for charge variant profiling with a sensitivity of 1 ng protein on-chip. Charge variants were electrophoretically separated and further characterized by accurate mass measurements after deconvolution. Accurate mass measurements at the level of a mAb require a mass resolution of 35,000 and adapted ion optics to transmit the heavy ions with few charges (high m/z ratios). As for other CE systems, localization of the modification sites is not possible and was based on a comparison of the electrophoretic separation with an earlier published chromatographic profile of trastuzumab. The authors concluded further that the resolving power of their system had limitations, particularly for the separation of isomerized form(s).

4. Mass spectrometry for the identification of deamidation products

Mass spectrometry (MS) is an indispensable tool to analyze the deamidation of Asn and Gln in therapeutic proteins. As outlined in the previous paragraph, MS alone is insufficient to give unambiguous answers and needs to be combined with liquid-chromatography (LC-MS). This is mainly due to the fact that some of the products of the deamidation reaction are isobaric (e.g. Asp and isoAsp, see Fig. 1). In addition, the first ¹³C-isotopologue of the usually more abundant Asn containing peptide, which has a mass increase of 1.003355 u, is very close in m/z value to the mass increase of 0.984016 u resulting from deamidation due to the replacement of an NH₂ group with an OH group. This rather small difference in mass cannot be discriminated unless a high-resolution mass analyzer is used. For example, for discriminating the first ¹³C-isotopologue of the native (non-deamidated) peptide IYPT-NGYTR in the heavy-chain CDR of trastuzumab from the monoisotopic peak of the deamidated peptide (IYPTD/isoDG YTR), the mass analyzer would need to work at a resolution of at least 60,000 ($\frac{m/z}{\Delta m} = \frac{1084.5}{0.019339}$). While this may be possible in the case of product characterization and quality control, where the amount of rather pure protein is not limiting, this is much more challenging in bioanalysis (see next paragraph), where the target protein has to be analyzed in a complex biological matrix and where triple quadrupole mass analyzers in the SRM mode working at a resolution of 1000–2000, are most commonly used due to their better sensitivity. The chromatographic separation of the non-deamidated Asn, the Asp and the iso-Asp containing peptides is thus indispensable. Such separations are impossible at the protein level or at least very challenging, as shown in previous paragraphs.

While Asp- and isoAsp-containing peptides are isobaric, there are biochemical approaches to discriminate between them by mass spectrometry or better by LC-MS. The enzyme L-isospartyl methyltransferase (PMT) transfers a methyl group from S-adenosyl-L-methionine

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of the proteolytic digestion of an IgG with IdeS followed by reduction of disulfide bonds resulting in Fd', Lc (light chain) and Fc/2 fragments of approximately 25 kDa each. This figure is reprinted with permission from Ref [64].

(SAM) to the side-chain carboxylic acid of iso-Asp residues in an attempt to mark them for repair. PIMT can also transfer a methyl group from SAM to D-Asp-residues, which may occur due to racemization during the deamidation reaction albeit at a much lower frequency. Converting an iso-Asp residue into the methyl ester increases its mass by 14 Da, which is easily detectable by commonly used mass spectrometers. Moreover, methylation increases the hydrophobicity of the corresponding peptide leading to a longer retention time upon RPLC. Another way of discriminating between Asp- and iso-Asp in a peptide is by digesting it with the protease Asp-N, which cleaves C-terminally to L-Asp-but not to iso-Asp or D-Asp. In this way Asp- and iso-Asp containing peptides can be discriminated in a comparative peptide map. This opens different ways of analysing the products of deamidation in detail by combining mass spectrometry with liquid chromatography and biochemical reactions.

There is a strong drive to develop mass spectrometric methods that allow analysing modifications in therapeutic proteins at the protein level without prior digestion. The main advantage of such an approach is that all modifications are analysed in the context of the entire protein and can thus be linked to specific variants. This connectivity is lost when digesting the protein prior to LC-MS analysis. Next to the need to purify specific variants or at least to enrich them considerably, there is also a need for efficient fragmentation methods that work for high-molecular weight, multiply-charged precursor ions. mAbs are on the upper end of the molecular weight scale of what is currently possible in that respect. With a 1 Da mass difference, deamidations are one of the most challenging modifications to analyze by MS. There are only a few studies, where top-down MS at the protein level has been used to characterize post-translational modifications (PTMs) including deamidations [11,62]. In these studies, top-down MS analysis of relatively small proteins in the range of 10–30 kDa was performed using different fragmentation techniques and deamidation sites were identified based on MS/MS fragments. To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies where top-down MS was performed for the analysis of deamidation in entire monoclonal antibodies. Here, with top-down MS we refer to the intact mass measurement followed by MS/MS fragmentation [63]. However, there are studies where deamidated variants were studied by accurate mass measurements at high mass resolution after separation by ion-exchange chromatography [30,43–46]. In these studies, variants that elute earlier than the main form from a cation-exchange column and that have a mass increase of about 1 Da (in case of a single deamidation) were assigned as deamidated variant(s). However, since there

was no MS/MS fragmentation, localization of deamidation sites was impossible and assignments relied only on mass shifts. In the end, deamidation sites were identified by the bottom-up approach after fractionation of the corresponding variants. These studies take a step forward by coupling IEX to MS in the analysis of deamidated variants at the intact protein level. However, as mentioned in chapter 2.1, there are specific technical requirements for the MS, and not every laboratory might be capable to perform such measurements compared to the bottom-up approach, which is a routine method. Accurate mass measurement of 1 Da mass increase is often not unambiguous, since it is around 7 ppm out of 150 kDa (approximate molecular weight of an antibody). It is relatively common to have a mass deviation of more than 7 ppm when the intact mass of such a big protein is measured. Another challenge may arise in the assignment of a variant that is deamidated in two positions. On a cation-exchange column, this variant will elute earlier than the main variant as an acidic variant. While accurate intact mass measurements can show around a 2 Da mass increase compared to the main variant, a variant that has deamidations in two positions is not the only possible reason for a 2 Da mass increase, since an acidic variant due to impaired cysteine (free SH groups) will also result in a 2 Da higher mass. Discrimination of these two acidic variants by only intact mass measurement won't be possible in such a scenario.

Since there are still technical limitations in performing top-down analysis of antibodies, researchers have resorted to a compromise by first dissociating antibodies into more manageable subunits through a combination of disulfide bond reduction (inter- and/or intra-chain) and enzymatic digestion with highly specific proteases that cleave in the region between the Fab and the Fc part (Fig. 6). Digestion by IdeS, a protease originally isolated from *Streptococcus pyogenes* [65], followed by disulfide bond reduction results in 25 kDa subunits that are more amenable to MS analysis as well as to separation by LC or CE [66]. However, part of the connectivity of the different modifications in a given variant is again lost and cannot be unambiguously reconstructed. Kelleher et al. compared different fragmentation methods in terms of sequence coverage for mAb subunits showing that Electron Transfer Dissociation (ETD), UV PhotoDissociation (UVPD) and the combination of ETD with higher energy collisional Dissociation (EThcD) are complementary giving on the order of 70 – 90% sequence coverage for LC, Fd and Fc/2 subunits (Fig. 7) [67]. These values decrease to around 40% for the heavy- and the light chain, respectively, when working at the intact mAb level. While impressive when it comes to the

Fig. 7. Representation of sequence coverage obtained with different MS fragmentation methods for the IdeS-generated ~25 kDa subunits of the mAb rituximab. The left sides of panels A–C show the fragmentation maps of Fd, Lc, and Fc/2 subunits, respectively, obtained by summing data from three ETD runs, two UVPD runs, and one ETHcD run (total of six LC–MS2 runs). The presence of the N-linked glycan mapped using diagnostic fragment ions which include the mass of the sugar chains G0F, G1F, and G2F, is highlighted by an orange rectangle. For each panel, the right side shows the corresponding Venn diagram of shared/unique matched fragment ions for each of the three MS fragmentation techniques. Reprinted with permission from L. Fornelli, K. Srzentić, R. Huguët, C. Mullen, S. Sharma, V. Zabrouskov, R.T. Fellers, K.R. Durbin, P.D. Compton, N.L. Kelleher, Accurate Sequence Analysis of a Monoclonal Antibody by Top-Down and Middle-Down Orbitrap Mass Spectrometry Applying Multiple Ion Activation Techniques, *Anal. Chem.* 90 (2018) 8421–8429. Copyright 2018 American Chemical Society.

power of high-resolution MS in combination with different fragmentation methods, these results show that modifications will be missed when falling into one of the regions that was not covered. Nevertheless, there are studies in the literature, where the so-called middle-down approach was used for characterization of deamidation by MS/MS fragmentation of subunits after IdeS digestion and reduction of disulfide bonds. Resemann et al. identified deamidation in the Fd subunit of cetuximab after middle-down matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization (MALDI) in-source decay (ISD) MS analysis [68]. Subunits were fractionated after subunit level reversed-phase LC separation. Collected fractions were directly spotted on the MALDI plate followed by middle-down MALDI ISD MS. The source of deamidation was the removal of the N-glycosylation site in the Fd domain by PNGase F. Native (non-deamidated) and deamidated Fd domains were not separated chromatographically, however,

were distinguished by their MS/MS fragments. In another study by Belov et al. subunits of an unspecified IgG1 after IdeS digestion followed by reduction were separated by capillary zone electrophoresis (CZE) prior to middle-down MS [69]. Deamidation was localized in the Fc/2 domain of the antibody, which was baseline separated by CZE.

While there are improvements in the analysis of antibody deamidation by accurate mass measurement and by middle-down MS, there is a need for further developments in mass spectrometry and protein separation. Currently, characterization of the major charge variants after (partial) separation by cation-exchange chromatography (CEX), fractionation, and further characterization by different analytical tools remain a commonly used approach. While this review focuses on deamidation as one of the major modifications in therapeutic mAbs, it must be kept in mind that Asn deamidation is not the only modification that has been

observed in mAbs. The combination of multiple, divergent modifications in mAb variants makes it extremely challenging to analyze them in the context of the entire protein from a separation as well as from a mass spectrometry point of view.

5. Bioanalysis of monoclonal antibody deamidation in biological samples

The analysis of therapeutic proteins, including mAbs in biological samples (plasma, serum, tissue), is most often done by ligand binding assays (mostly immunoassays), but this methodology is not suitable to decipher the various variants (proteoforms) that may occur due to deamidation and other PTMs, as variant-specific affinity binders are generally not available. The bioanalysis of deamidation products of mAbs is thus mainly performed by LC-MS at the peptide level after enzymatic digestion. Optimization of conditions for enzymatic digestion is of utmost importance since enzymatic reactions with widely used proteases like trypsin and Lys-C have their pH optimum at basic pH and require elevated temperatures and prolonged reaction times for optimal digestion, which may cause artificial deamidation during sample preparation and thus lead to an overestimation of the degree of deamidation. While a compromise may be found by performing digestions at neutral or slightly acidic pH and for shorter times, the efficiency of digestion is affected, and it must be assessed whether a given signature peptide is reproducibly released to perform quantitative analyses, for example, by LC-MS in the selected reaction monitoring (SRM) or the parallel reaction monitoring (PRM) mode. Optimizing digestion conditions is clearly a much more challenging task when attempting to perform a complete peptide map of a given mAb to detect unknown deamidation sites, since artificial deamidation cannot be avoided if a complete digest must be reached. It is thus very important to discriminate the level of deamidation induced due to sample preparation from the level of deamidation that was present in the original sample. One way of approaching this challenge is by taking samples at various time points of the digestion reaction and to plot the level of deamidation at different sites against the digestion time and to relate this to the overall level of digestion. However, most often a compromise must be found. To overcome this limitation, a Lys-C variant has been engineered that has its pH optimum in the slightly acidic pH region, where spontaneous deamidation is much slower [52,70]. While there are other proteases with pH optima in the acidic pH range, they are not as specific as trypsin or Lys-C and are not widely used in the analysis of therapeutic mAbs [71,72].

Artificial deamidation during sample preparation can be reduced or avoided by integrated multidimensional online systems [73]. Gstöttner et al. reported the development of a 4D-LC-MS/MS workflow for the characterization of charge variants by online peptide mapping [74]. In the first dimension, charge variants were separated on a CEX column followed by on-column reduction of fractions collected from the first dimension. It should be mentioned that fractions from the first dimension were collected online and stored in loops. An immobilized trypsin cartridge served as the third dimension where tryptic digestion was performed in flow-through mode. The last dimension was a regular reversed-phase separation of tryptic peptides, which was coupled to mass spectrometry. In this way, artificial modifications due to manual fraction collection or during tryptic digestion can be avoided or minimized.

Reproducibility of peptide mapping analysis can be improved by automated digestion protocols where the enzymatic (mainly tryptic) digestion step is accelerated to achieve an efficient and reproducible sample preparation method. The enzymatic digestion step is believed to affect the reproducibility of peptide mapping analysis and conditions used for enzymatic digestion are known to introduce artificial modifications, notably deamidations. Important parameters to optimize comprise digestion pH, temperature, and time. Several approaches have been proposed to reduce the digestion time including the use of ultrasound, microwave irradiation or infrared assisted digestion [75]. Recently, Millan-Martin

et al. published a report on an inter-laboratory study where peptide mapping was performed using an automated system where an immobilized trypsin kit was used [76]. Results obtained from four different laboratories using the same peptide mapping protocol showed good correlation in terms of PTM mapping including deamidation. The drawback of the reported automated protocol is the utilization of high temperature (70 °C) during digestion, which may induce artificial deamidation despite the short digestion time of 30 min.

In a study where deamidation of Hc-Asn-55 on the heavy chain CDR2 of trastuzumab was measured in the clinical samples, Bults et al. performed tryptic digestion at pH 7 and 37 °C for three hours showing that artificial deamidation was below 1% at this site under these conditions. Another alternative is performing digestion under basic conditions but shortening the digestion time and increasing the enzyme-to-substrate ratio as shown by Mehl et al. [77]. These authors performed tryptic digestion in 50 mM ammonium bicarbonate buffer for 2 h at 37 °C where the trypsin to protein ratio was 1:5. The amount of artificial deamidation was negligible under these conditions.

The bioanalysis of mAbs in complex samples like plasma or serum requires sample preparation. When using LC-MS in the SRM or PRM mode, it is often sufficient to precipitate all proteins and to perform an 'on-pellet digestion'. Such an approach gives satisfactory results down to the µg/mL concentration level [78]. This is mainly due to the limited loadability of the chromatographic column, which is largely occupied by peptides that are derived from other plasma/serum proteins. When lower concentration levels must be reached or when a more comprehensive analysis is required (e.g. a complete peptide map), it is necessary to enrich mAbs using different affinity binders prior to LC-MS analysis. This results in hybrid ligand binding – LC-MS assays (LBA/LC-MS), which combine the characteristics and the limitations of the affinity binder that recognizes a given epitope or binding site on the mAb, with the selectivity of LC-MS, which is based on retention time and characteristic m/z values of the peptide ions and their fragments. With such an approach, it is, for example, possible that certain variants may not be recognized by the affinity binder and thus escape further analysis.

Often highly specific binders that are directed against the unique CDRs of therapeutic mAbs are used for such purposes, as they must discriminate the mAb from the more abundant endogenous antibodies. However, if deamidation occurs in the CDRs, the selected binders may no longer recognize the deamidated forms, a point that needs to be assessed. Immunopurification using an anti-human Fc capture antibody is a more generic approach to enrich mAbs from plasma/serum samples while removing non-antibody plasma proteins such as albumin. In the studies by Huang et al. [6] and Mehl et al. [77], antibodies directed against the Fc part of a human IgG1 were used for the isolation and further quantification of *in vivo* deamidation of the corresponding antibodies from monkey serum. This approach is thus particularly suited for preclinical studies, while the presence of the large excess of endogenous IgGs needs to be considered when it comes to human samples.

There are several ways to approach the quantification of deamidated protein variants at the peptide level after enzymatic digestion. For the native (non-deamidated) form, a calibration curve can be easily prepared using the original mAb as a reference standard, digestion of which will yield the non-deamidated surrogate peptide for LC-MS quantification. However, such an approach cannot be directly applied for the deamidated forms, because of the typical lack of pure reference standards for the deamidated forms of intact mAbs. Instead, quantification can be performed by using calibration samples containing the native and deamidated surrogate peptides, which are much easier to obtain in pure form. A disadvantage of using deamidated peptides rather than proteins for calibration is that they do not account for the possibly incomplete digestion efficiency of the protein analytes. Therefore, the digestion may require separate optimization to ensure completeness, or a correction factor may have to be applied. Alternatively, the LC-MS response of the non-deamidated surrogate peptide, obtained after cleavage of the non-deamidated protein in the calibration samples, is also used for

quantification of the deamidated protein forms in study samples. For example, Bults et al. used the LC-MS responses of the tryptic peptides IYPTNGYTR, IYPTDGYTR, and IYPTisoDGYTR for the quantification of deamidation in the CDR2 of the heavy chain of trastuzumab in patient plasma [54]. Since the response of the deamidated peptides was demonstrated to be equal to that of the native peptide IYPTNGYTR, the calibration curve containing non-deamidated trastuzumab was also used for the quantification of the deamidated forms of trastuzumab. Similarly, Mehl et al. performed quantification of deamidated forms of mAbs, assuming that MS ionization of native and deamidated peptides would not be very different [77].

6. Conclusions and future perspectives

mAbs are known to undergo chemical modifications such as asparagine deamidation, aspartate isomerization and oxidation of methionine and tryptophan residues. Those modifications are of utmost interest when they occur in the CDRs of mAbs since CDRs are involved in antigen binding. A number of cases where the activity of mAbs was affected by deamidation in the CDRs have been reported in the literature [4,24,39,79,80]. In case deamidation in CDRs has a negative impact on the biological activity of a particular antibody, it is included in the list of critical quality attributes (CQA). In the ICH Q8 guideline, a CQA is defined as a physical, chemical, biological, or microbiological property or characteristic that should be within an appropriate limit, range, or distribution to ensure the desired product quality [81]. Here, CQA requirements apply to the production process. Even if we assume that the level of the above-mentioned chemical modifications can be controlled during production, concern arises about stability during storage and *in vivo*. *In vivo* modifications after drug administration, so-called “*in vivo* biotransformation”, is a more recent aspect that has attracted the attention of scientists due to possible implications for the therapeutic efficacy of a mAb [82,83]. *In vivo* conditions such as the slightly basic pH of human blood and the temperature of the human body may induce deamidation. Revealing the effect of deamidation in the CDRs on the efficacy of a drug may require additional pre-clinical studies in combination with the bioanalysis of mAb variants that arise after drug administration [84,85].

While deamidation is a widely studied post-translational modification (PTM) in proteins and notably in therapeutic mAbs, it is a rather difficult task to elucidate all of the variants that may occur in such a large protein due to deamidation, let alone in combination with other possible PTMs. A simple ‘Gedankenexperiment’ makes this clear. Let us assume that we have 3 different deamidation sites, one in the light chain (Lc) and two in the heavy chain (Hc). This would result in 2 possible variants for the Lc and 4 possible variants for the Hc. As each variant of the Lc can combine with one of the 4 variants of the Hc, this would result in 8 Lc-Hc combinations. Since each mAb contains 2 Lc and 2 Hc, this allows for the potential formation of 36 different variants based on only 3 deamidation sites. This combinatoric could be taken further by including the formation of Asp- or isoAsp as products of the deamidation reaction, again resulting in different variants, followed by the inclusion of other PTMs such as the oxidation of Met. If we even consider the numerous possibilities of glycoforms [86], we quickly end up with hundreds if not thousands of possible variants of a single mAb. Suffices to say that there is no analytical methodology available today (and likely not in the foreseeable future either) that could attempt to separate such a complex protein mixture nor any methodology, including mass spectrometry, that could deconvolute it with or without partial prior separation.

What are then the challenges lying ahead and what are the compromises that we have to make? First and foremost, we need better protein separation methods. With respect to chromatography, it is certain that we need to make use of multi-dimensional chromatographic (MD-LC) systems that use different modes of interaction between mAbs and the stationary phase. There are some notable examples in the literature that

employ fully automated MD-LC systems for protein separation [73,87–90]. However, MS analysis at the protein level is still facing considerable challenges, as outlined in this review, and it is currently unclear whether these principle limitations (e.g. the distribution of the signal over many charge states; the difficulty of fragmenting large protein ions) can be overcome in the foreseeable future. It will thus be necessary to combine MD-LC with enzymatic digestion reactions after denaturation, reduction and alkylation to either dissociate the mAb variants into subunits and/or to digest them fully into peptides followed by LC-MS analysis. Integrating such complex sample preparation workflows remains a challenge even today. There is much to be said in favor of automated sample handling and sample preparation systems in combination with MD-LC, notably in the context of characterizing therapeutic proteins, since these analyses must comply with stringent quality criteria. Manual handling of samples is not only time-consuming and thus often prohibitively expensive for multiple variants per mAb, it also carries the risk of introducing artefacts, for example in terms of increasing levels of deamidation. While considerable progress has been made in integrating MD-LC systems with downstream sample preparation, these systems are currently at the research level and do not show the robustness needed for industrial (routine) applications.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Baubek Spanov: Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Natalia Govorukhina:** Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Nico C. van de Merbel:** Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Rainer Bischoff:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.

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